

MODEL OF THERMOMECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF POLYMERS IN GLASS TRANSITION STATE AND ITS APPLICATION TO THE ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL STRESSES IN POLYMERS

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SUMMARY: A mathematical model is presented to describe the evolution of the stress-strain state in fiber-reinforced composites with a plastic binder capable of glass transition. The model is based on the phenomenological methods of continuum mechanics and phenomenological macrokinetics of the chemical-physical processes (polymerization, glass transition) in a plastic binder. A set of experiments has been specified to identify the model parameters. Numerical solutions are presented which demonstrate the effectiveness of the model. With this model we have described the evolution of engineering and residual stresses as well as polymerization and glass transition processes in a hybrid composite manufactured by hot molding in a curing autoclave. A numerical analysis has been carried out to calculate the dependence of engineering and residual stresses in a composite under different manufacturing conditions and to define the process parameters which provide a minimum level of residual stresses.

KEYWORDS: technological stresses, glass transition, polymerization, numerical modeling.

INTRODUCTION

Formulation of the problem

Consider a hybrid composite plate with a honeycombed filler produced by a subsequent stacking of carbon and organic fibers impregnated with a binding thermoreactive epoxy resin polymerized and cured in a curing autoclave. Polymerization is carried out at specific temperature and pressure to provide the completeness of the process. Then a polymerized and cured composition is cooled down from the temperature exceeding the glass transition temperature to $\cong 20^\circ \text{C}$.

Thermochemical study.

Suppose that the desired temperature fields and polymerization degrees depend here only on the coordinate z , normal to the plane of composite layers, and time t . Heat dissipation over the multilayer composite plate is found from

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + \rho Q, \quad (1)$$

$$t \in (0, t_k], z \in (0, H),$$

where $Q = (\partial\alpha/\partial t)Q_R$ is the rate of heat release in the course of polymerization, Q_R is the total amount of released heat, $\rho = \rho(z)$, $k = k(z)$, $c = c(z)$ are the density, the heat conductivity coefficient and the heat capacity of a certain composite layer, and $\alpha = \alpha(z, t)$ is the polymerization (curing) degree of the binder.

Equation (1) is closed by the initial conditions

$$T(z, 0) = T_H(z), \quad z \in [0, H] \quad (2)$$

and the boundary conditions

$$k \frac{\partial T(0, t)}{\partial z} = h(T(0, t) - T_0(t)) \frac{\partial T(0, t)}{\partial z} = 0,$$

$$-k \frac{\partial T(H, t)}{\partial z} = h(T(H, t) - T_c(t)), \quad t \in (0, t_k], \quad (3)$$

where H is the thickness of a laminated composite plate, $T_H(z)$ is the initial temperature of the layers, h is the heat transfer to the environment, and $T_c(z)$ is the time-temperature dependence of a medium round the external composite layers.

The system of eqn. (1)-(3) is solved together with the macrokinetic equation for the polymerization degree of an epoxy binder [1] as

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = K_B \exp(-E_B/RT) (1 - \alpha)(1 + c_0 \alpha),$$

$$t \in (0, t_k], \quad z \in [0, H];$$

$$\alpha(z, 0) = 0, \quad z \in [0, H], \quad (4)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, E_B is the activation energy of the process, K_B is the normalizing multiplier, and α is the relative value taking the values from 0 to 1 and characterizing the extent to which the reaction of polymerization proceeds.

Thermomechanical study.

Upon the completion of polymerization, the composite binder is in the highelasticity temperature range beyond the glass transition temperature T_g . From this point on the composite cooling and the binder glass transition start. Physical relations, continuously describing the interaction between stress tensors and deformations $\hat{\sigma}, \hat{\epsilon}$ in relaxation transition of the composite from highelasticity to glassy state, are based on the phenomenological approach [2,3].

The stress state is assumed, for the laminated composite plate under study, homogeneous within a layer and changeable only in layer-to-layer transition. The laminated composite plate will be considered in a system of coordinates (α, β, z) (Fig.1). With allowance made for the stacking geometry and the following expressions:

Fig. 1

$$F_1^k(\hat{\epsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\bar{R}_{\alpha\alpha}^k (\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k)^2 + 2\bar{R}_{\alpha\beta}^k \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k + \bar{R}_{\beta\beta}^k (\epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k)^2 \right],$$

$$F_2^k(\hat{\epsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\tilde{R}_{\alpha\alpha}^k (\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k)^2 + 2\tilde{R}_{\alpha\beta}^k \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k + \tilde{R}_{\beta\beta}^k (\epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k)^2 \right],$$

physical relations for the k th composite layer in a system of coordinates (α, β) are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^k(t) = & \bar{R}_{\alpha\alpha}^k \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(t) + \tilde{R}_{\alpha\alpha}^k \int_{T_H^k}^{T^k(t)} [\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(t) - \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(\tau)] dN[T(\tau)] + \bar{R}_{\alpha\beta}^k \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(t) + \\ & + \tilde{R}_{\alpha\beta}^k \int_{T_H^k}^{T^k(t)} [\epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(t) - \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(\tau)] dN[T(\tau)], \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\beta\beta}^k(t) = & \bar{R}_{\beta\alpha}^k \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(t) + \tilde{R}_{\beta\alpha}^k \int_{T_H^k}^{T^k(t)} [\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(t) - \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k(\tau)] dN[T(\tau)] + \bar{R}_{\beta\beta}^k \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(t) + \\ & + \tilde{R}_{\beta\beta}^k \int_{T_H^k}^{T^k(t)} [\epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(t) - \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k(\tau)] dN[T(\tau)], \end{aligned}$$

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k = \epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k - \int_{T_H^k}^{T^k(t)} \alpha_{\alpha\alpha}^k(T) dT, \quad \tilde{R}_{ij}^k = R_{ij}^k - \bar{R}_{ij}^k, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^k, \sigma_{\beta\beta}^k$ are the stress tensor components, $\epsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k, \epsilon_{\beta\beta}^k$ are the full strain tensor components, \bar{R}_{ij}^k are the generalized rigidities of the k th composite layer with a binder in highelasticity state, R_{ij}^k are the generalized rigidities of the k th composite layer with a binder

in glassy state; $\alpha_{\alpha\alpha}^k(T)$ are the temperature coefficients of thermal expansion of the k th composite layer, T_H^k is the final temperature of polymerization of the binder in the k th composite layer, and $T^k(t)$ is the current temperature in the k th composite layer.

Phenomenologically, the increase in rigidity of the binder in glass transition at the cost of new links generated on the sectional and intermolecular levels can be treated as a probability process. Then the rate of change of the glass transition degree with temperature is described by the normal law of distribution

$$\frac{dN}{dT} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\gamma}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{T-T_g}{\gamma}\right)^2\right], \quad (6)$$

where the dispersion γ is determined through the value of the glass transition temperature range: $\gamma = (T_{g1} - T_{g2})/\delta$, and the mathematical expectation T_g is taken as the glass transition temperature.

It should be noted that for each layer, until the process of polymerization is finished, σ_{ij}^k and ε_{ij}^k are assumed equal to zero. Suppose that the polymerized composite layers deform simultaneously. The equilibrium equation

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^i(t) h_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_{\beta\beta}^i(t) h_i = 0 \quad (7)$$

gives the joint strains $\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}(t)$ and $\varepsilon_{\beta\beta}(t)$.

The values of generalized rigidities R_{ij}^k and R_{ij}^k , corresponding to highelasticity and glassy states, are calculated by formally equal relations [4]

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\alpha\alpha}^k &= E_1^k \cos^4 \varphi_k + E_2^k \sin^4 \varphi_k + 2(E_1^k \nu_{12}^k + 2G_{12}^k) \sin^2 \varphi_k \cos^2 \varphi_k, \\ R_{\alpha\beta}^k &= \bar{E}_1^k \nu_{12}^k + \left[\bar{E}_1^k + \bar{E}_2^k - 2(E_1^k \nu_{12}^k + 2G_{12}^k) \right] \sin^2 \varphi_k \cos^2 \varphi_k, \\ R_{\beta\beta}^k &= E_1^k \sin^4 \varphi_k + E_2^k \cos^4 \varphi_k + 2(E_1^k \nu_{12}^k + 2G_{12}^k) \sin^2 \varphi_k \cos^2 \varphi_k, \\ \alpha_{\alpha\alpha}^k &= \alpha_1^k \cos^2 \varphi_k - \alpha_2^k \sin^2 \varphi_k, \\ \alpha_{\beta\beta}^k &= \alpha_1^k \sin^2 \varphi_k + \alpha_2^k \cos^2 \varphi_k, \\ \bar{E}_{1,2}^k &= E_{1,2}^k / (1 - \nu_{12}^k \nu_{21}^k), \quad E_1^k \nu_{12}^k = E_2^k \nu_{21}^k, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where E_{12}^k is the elasticity modules in directions 1 and 2, G_{12}^k is the shear module in the layer plane, ν_{12}^k, ν_{21}^k are Poisson's ratios, α_1^k, α_2^k are the temperature coefficients of linear expansion along axes 1 and 2.

Experimental support of the model

One main stage to experimentally support the thermomechanical part is to define the parameters of equation (4) describing the degree of advancement of polymerization α which is related to a certain rate of heat release Q and the full specific heat release Q_R by $Q = (\partial\alpha/\partial t)Q_R$

Here, we need to define the following parameters: the normalizing coefficient K_B , the activation energy E_B , the constant value c_0 , and a specific heat release Q_R .

For experiment, a dynamic scanning microcalorimeter was used to measure a specific rate of heat release in the course of polymerization of an alcohol - acetone epoxy binder under isothermal conditions and $Q_R \approx 5450$ cal/kg. Experimental results are given in Fig. 2. A simultaneous treatment of the four experimental curves yielded $K_B = 2155,24 \text{ c}^{-1}$; $E_B = 5 \cdot 10^4$ J/mol ; $c_0 = 3,58$ J/mol.

To determine the temperature range of glass transition of an epoxy binder and its deformation properties, particularly at $T > T_g$, the cured epoxy samples were tested thermomechanically on the setup allowing one to measure the temperature of structural glass transition and viscoelastic state in the temperature range from -150° to 400° , and to investigate the deformation of polymers subjected to uniaxial compression with time at different temperatures.

Fig. 2. A specific rate of heat release in the process of polymerization of the epoxy binder under isothermal conditions: 1 - $T = 120^\circ$, 2 - 110° , 3 - 100° , 4 - 90° .

Fig. 3 presents the results of thermomechanical tests on the epoxy samples obtained under different schemes of thermomechanical loading. From experiments it follows that the

temperatures of the beginning and completion of glass transition are $T_{g1}=109^\circ$ and $T_{g2}=103^\circ$, respectively, and the glass transition temperature $T_g=106^\circ$.

Numerical algorithm and results

To solve the boundary value problem (1) - (3), the finite-element method is used. Based on the integrointerpolation method [5], the conservative difference scheme, converging to the class of piecewise continuous coefficients, is constructed on the uniform mesh $\bar{\omega}_{h\tau} = \bar{\omega}_h \times \bar{\omega}_\tau$,

$$\bar{\omega}_h = \{z_i = h_z i \mid i = 0, N_z, h_z = H/N_z\}, \quad \bar{\omega}_\tau = \{t_m = m\tau \mid m = 0, N_\tau, \tau = t_k/N_\tau\}.$$

Fig. 3. Thermomechanical plots for the binder specimen: 1, 2 - heating at $T = 5$ deg/min at the load 250g, 2, 3 - cooling at $T = 2.5$ deg/min, 5, 6 - cooling at $T = 2.5$ deg/min without loading.

The equation with the initial condition (4) at each mesh node $\bar{\omega}_h$ at each time step t_{m+1} is solved using the fourth-order Runge-Cutta method [6].

The following thermophysical material characteristics were used. Organoplastic (o): $\rho = 1380$ kg/m³, $c=1400$ J/kg/K, $k=0,012$ W/m/K, the layer thickness $h_{op}=0,16 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. Carbon plastic (c) $\rho = 1500$ kg/m³, $c=1000$ J/kg/K, $k = 0,012$ W/m/K, the layer thickness $h_{cp} = 0,18 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. Honeycombed filler: $\rho = 6$ kg/m³, $c = 1000$ J/kg/K, $k = 0,95$ W/m/K, the layer thickness $h_c=0,02$ m.

Numerical experiments show that since the environmental temperature increases slowly (2 degrees per minute), then the temperature gradient in the layers of a composite plate is small regardless the heat transfer coefficients chosen. On this basis the coefficient $h = 10$ W/m/K was taken. On heating and cooling, the temperature difference between the internal and external organoplastic layers does not exceed 1.5 degree.

Fig. 4 provides the results of calculations of the mean temperature and the polymerization degree in the internal (T_B, α_B) and the external coverings (T_H, α_H) with the prescribed regularity of temperature changes $T_c(t)$.

The internal covering consists of the layers placed in the following sequence: o(45°), c(0°), c(0°), c(0°), c(0°), o(45°), and the external: o(45°), c(0°), c(0°), o(45°), c(0°), c(0°), o(45°), where the angle between the direction of the layer base and the direction α is shown in parentheses. The process of polymerization lasts 2.4 h and 2.8 h for the internal and external coverings, respectively. Further exposure up to 4 h at $T_c=125^\circ$ does not affect the binder. Thus, the exposure for 3 h exceeds the necessary approximately by the factor of two.

Fig. 4. Time dependence of the environmental temperature T_c (dashed line) and the mean temperature in the layers of internal and external coverings (solid line) and the corresponding degrees of polymerization α .

Based on the solution to the thermochemical problem, we calculated engineering and residual stresses from eqn. (5) -(8). The initial data for the mechanical characteristics of the composite layers and filler were assumed as follows:

- Organoplastic: $E_{11} = (2,766 - 0,00997 T) \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $E_{22} = (2,4213 - 0,008915 T) \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $G_{12} = 0,25 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $\nu_{12} = 0,11$, $\alpha_{11} = (4 - 0,09 T - 10^{-3} T^2) \cdot 10^{-6}$ K⁻¹, $\alpha_{22} = (4 + 0,1117 T - 0,002417 T^2) \cdot 10^{-6}$ K⁻¹;
- Carbon plastic: $E_{11} = (1,41 - 0,0013 T) \cdot 10^{11}$ Pa, $E_{22} = (1 - 0,00875 T) \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $G_{12} = 0,535 \cdot 10^{10}$ Pa, $\nu_{12} = 0,35$, $\alpha_{11} = (-0,4 - 0,005 T) \cdot 10^{-6}$ K⁻¹, $\alpha_{22} = 20 \cdot 10^{-6}$ K⁻¹;
- Honeycombed filler. $E = 2,068 \cdot 10^8$ Pa, $G_{12} = 1,034 \cdot 10^8$ Pa.

Numerical experiments also demonstrate that in calculations it is possible to treat the honeycombed plate in the plane $\alpha\beta$ as isotropic.

Of interest is the estimation of the effect of viscoelastic properties of the binder in a glassy state and organic fibers on the level of residual stresses. For this, an approximate approach [7] is used which suggests the change of the elastic constant \bar{R}_{ij}^k to the appropriate "variables" of the rigidity $\bar{R}_{ij}^k(\xi_k(t))$, where the up-dated time for the k th layer $\xi_k(t)$ is defined as

$\xi_k(t) = \int_0^t a_{T_k}(T_k(\tau)) d\tau$, where a_{T_k} is the function of time-temperature shear of the k th material layer, and the time is counted from the moment of the completion of glass transition ($T \leq T_{g2}$) in the layer.

For the unidirectional carbon plastic layer, creep along fibers was not considered and in transverse direction the viscoelastic properties were specified by the binder properties.

In general, until the binder glass transition finishes, the stress state of the composite does not practically depend on a thermal treatment, if heating and cooling are done at low speed. This is due to the small thickness of the composite covering and its rapid warm-up and cooling. The level of transverse stresses in carbon plastic can be decreased by changing the plate structure, for example, by placing the unidirectional layers in the direction β .

Fig. 5

Fig. 5 demonstrates the time dependence of stress tensor components in the internal covering layers on cooling: the solid line gives the elastic case, the dashed line gives the case with the allowance made for the viscoelastic properties of the binder and organic fibers. The symmetric stacking of layers with respect to the axes α and β eliminates the tangential stresses $\tau_{\alpha\beta}$. Also presented on Fig. 5 is the change in stress tensor components at times when the temperature corresponds to the range of transition of the binder from viscoelastic to completely glassy state (at $t=8192$ s with $T > T_{g1}$ in all layers, and at $t = 8288$ s with $T < T_{g2}$). The numeral by the curve denotes the number of the layer in the internal covering counted off from the honeycombed layer to the external.

The stress values of different layers are practically similar at $t > 8300$ s, and Fig. 6, therefore, gives the averaged curves. The stresses σ_α and σ_β reach the highest values in organoplastic layers of the external covering and are compressive. It should be noted that the maximum value σ_β corresponds to $t = 9968$ s and the layer temperature $44,3^\circ$ exceeding the value of residual stress σ_β by 28 MPa (Fig. 6). Stresses in the carbon plastic layers in the direction of fibers arrangement (α) are tensile and reach 1.75 MPa in the external layers of the covering. Most dangerous are tensile stresses σ_β in the external carbon plastic covering (to 1,75 MPa at $t = 9968$ s), which comprises approximately 5% of the level of a short-term transverse tensile strength.

Fig. 6

Taking into account the creep yields 30-40% estimation of the magnitude of stress relaxation σ_{α} in the organoplastic and carbon plastic layers. Transverse stresses σ_{β} in a carbon plastic relax by 50 - 55 % . Almost all relaxation mechanisms have had time to act at rather high temperatures of cooling and practically have finished to $t = 10000$ s.

Conclusions

A mathematical model capable to describe temperature, chemical and mechanical processes during manufacture of a hybrid composite material by hot molding in a curing autoclave has been developed and solved numerically. A number of experiments were performed to define constants involved in the kinetic equation of polymerization of the binder.

The obtained numerical results allowed us to choose the optimal temperature exposure regimes for the articles and the structure of a laminated plate providing the decrease in transverse engineering stresses.

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